

INVESTOR SENTIMENT AND SOVEREIGN RISK: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM AN EMERGING MARKET.

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Abstract: This paper aims to test the relationship between investor sentiment and sovereign risk in Turkey for the period 2004-2010. Our findings support that there is no cointegration, in other words long term relationship between investor sentiment and sovereign risk. In short run, we find causality relationship from investor sentiment and sovereign risk. The findings of the paper is important for Turkish government officials and market participants.

Keywords: Investor sentiment, sovereign risk, cointegration, Granger causality

JEL Codes: C32, E44, G02

1. Introduction

The impact of investors' psychology on financial markets is a well-known phenomenon in the financial market literature. Although the standard finance theory which states that stock prices reflect the discounted value of expected cash-flows and irrationalities among market participants are neutralized by arbitrageurs, behavioral approach suggests that waves of irrational sentiment, i.e. optimistic or pessimistic expectations affect asset prices (Schmelling, 2009). Besides, individual investors do not trade dependently and are more likely to react market rumors at the same time in financial markets. If this herding effect does exist, market will be affected by systematic sentiments (Zang, 2010). After this point, the problem is how to measure investor sentiment and how to quantify the effects of sentimental factors.

In the literature, researchers examine investment sentiment from different perspectives. A large body of studies focus on measuring investor sentiment index accurately (Lee et.al., 1991; Neal and Wheatly, 1998; Brown and Cliff, 2004; Baker and Wurglar, 2007). From this studies, there exists two ways to measure investor sentiment in the literature. First of them is measuring investor sentiment through direct measurement. Direct measurement includes getting feedbacks from investors relation to their sentiments through questionnaire (Shiller, 2000). However, indirect

measurements focus on finding instruments proxied for investor sentiment (*investor mood*: Kamstra et.al, 2003; *mutual fund flows*, Frazzini and Lamonth, 2005; *trading volume or liquidity*, Baker and Stein, 2004; *dividend premium*, Baker and Wurgler, 2004; *closed-end fund discount*, Zweig, 1973; *retail investor trade*, Kumar and Lee, 2006). In addition to measuring investor sentiment, studies focus on the impact of investor sentiment on stock returns and volatility (Lee et.al., 2002, Schmeling, 2009) and corporate bond spread (Nayak, 2010) in the literature. Besides some studies aims to relate investor sentiment to financial crisis (Siegel, 1992; Zouaoui, 2010). Few studies have attempted to link investor sentiment to country or sovereign risk (Eichengreen and Mody, 1998; Diaz and Gemmill, 2006; Dumitic and Ridzak, 2011; Spyrou, 2011). For example, Eichengreen and Mody (1998) find that changes in spreads are mainly due to shifts in market sentiment rather than in fundamentals.

Motivated by these findings, this paper aims to examine the relationship between investor sentiment and sovereign risk for an emerging market, Turkey. The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 explains data and methodology, section 3 summarizes the findings and section 4 concludes the paper.

2. Data and Methodology

In this paper, we use monthly J.P Morgan's EMBI+ spread for the period 2004-2010 to proxy sovereign risk based on existing literature (Lemmon and Portniaguina, 2006; Schmelling, 2009). The EMBI+ index tracks foreign-currency denominated government bond yields for a number of emerging market economies and compares them to the yields of benchmark instruments issued by developed countries. EMBI+ index includes Brady bonds, benchmark Eurobonds, loans. The other variable used in this paper is investor sentiment. In the literature, different studies use various proxies for investor sentiment. Following Lemmon and Portniaguina (2006), we use monthly Consumer Confidence Index (henceforth, CCI) of Central Bank of Turkey (CBOT) as a proxy for investor sentiment in this paper. We have obtained EMBI+ and CCI data from Datastream and CBOT, respectively.

We examine the relationship between investor sentiment and sovereign risk by applying Vector Autoregression analysis (VAR). At first, we test the stationarity of variables by using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test (Dickey and Fuller, 1981) to prevent spurious regression results. If the variables are I(1), it is necessary to investigate cointegration relationship between variables. If there is cointegration relationship between variables, an error correction term must be included in the VAR model, otherwise, the variables must be included in the model by taking their first differences.

We use Johansen-Juselius (1990) procedure to test cointegration between variables. Johansen-Juselius procedure (1990) is defined as follows;

$$x_t = \beta_1 x_{t-1} + \beta_2 x_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{t-k} + \eta_t \quad [1]$$

In equation [1], x_t is vector of variables I(1), and η_t is vector of residuals. Equation [1] also can be written as in equation [2];

$$\Delta x_t = \Pi x_{t-k} + \Gamma_1 \Delta x_{t-1} + \Gamma_2 \Delta x_{t-2} + \dots + \Gamma_{k-1} \Delta x_{t-(k-1)} + \eta_t \quad [2]$$

$$\text{where, } \Pi = \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j \right) - I \quad \text{and} \quad \Gamma_i = \left(\sum_{j=1}^i \beta_j \right) - I$$

Johansen-Juselius (1990) test focuses on examination of the Π matrix. Π matrix is a long run coefficient matrix, since in equilibrium, all the Δy_{t-i} will be zero and setting the error terms, η_t , to their expected value of zero will leave $\Pi x_{t-k} = 0$. The cointegration between variables is calculated by looking at the rank of the Π matrix via its eigenvalue. Trace statistic and max eigenvalue statistic are used for cointegration under the Johansen-Juselius (1990) approach. Trace statistic and max eigenvalue statistic are calculated as follows:

$$\lambda_{trace}(r) = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^g \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_i) \quad \text{and} \\ \lambda_{max}(r, r+1) = -T \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_{r+1}) \quad [3]$$

where r is the number of cointegrating vectors under the null hypothesis and $\hat{\lambda}_i$ is the estimated value for the i^{th} ordered eigenvalue from the Π matrix (Brooks, 2002).

VAR(p) model can be defined as follows:

$$\Delta x_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta x_{t-i} + \xi_t \quad [4]$$

Where x_t is a $(n \times 1)$ vector of endogenous variables, c is the intercept vector of the VAR, ϕ_i is the matrix of autoregressive coefficients, ξ_t is the generalisation of white noise process. Lastly, we apply Granger Causality in a bivariate VAR to find the way of the causality.

$$\Delta x_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta x_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta y_{t-i} + v_t$$

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta x_{t-i} + \varphi_t \quad [5]$$

3. Empirical Findings

In this section, we summarise the findings of cointegration test, VAR and Granger Causality tests. Table.1 and Table.2 give the descriptive statistics and unit root test of variables respectively.

Table.1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

	LEMBI	LCCI
Mean	6.6006	4.5151
Maximum	6.9872	4.7176
Minimum	6.1986	4.2326
S.Dev	0.2098	0.1154
Skewness	0.2344	-0.4282
Kurtosis	2.1105	2.5339
JB statistics	3.9175	3.6844

Table.2: Results of Unit Root Test

		Level	
	Test statistic	Model	Lag
EMBI+	-0.1897	&	2
CCI	-2.1872	&	1
		First Difference	
	Test statistic	Model	Lag
EMBI+	-10.1412***	&	1
CCI	-6.4356***	&	0

Note: Null hypothesis is a statement that “series have unit root”. *** indicates %1 significance level. & represents “with intercept” model. We use Schwarz Information Criterion for lag order selection. Log transformation of EMBI and CCI is used .

It is clear from Table.2 that variables have unit root at level and become stationary when we take the first difference. Since series are I(1), there may be a cointegration relationship between these pair of variables. Thus, at a later stage we test the

cointegration relationship between variables by applying Johansen- Juselius (1990) procedure. Table.3 presents the findings of Johansen- Juselius (1990) cointegration test.

Table.3: Cointegration Test Results

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max- Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob
None	0.0490	4.4771	14.2646	0.8059
At most 1	0.0030	0.2761	3.8414	0.5992

Note: we used “2”lag based on Akaike and Schwarz criterions.

We can not reject both of the hypotheses which formed as “ there is no cointegrating vector between variables” and “there is at most 1 cointegrating vector between variables” in Table.3. Therefore, we can conclude that there is no cointegration relationship between EMBI+ index and investor sentiment.

Then, we estimate VAR (2) (according to Schwarz criterion) model by including variables in their

first differences. We give the findings of VAR-based Granger causality test results in Table 4. While we do not reject the hypothesis of “EMBI does not Granger Cause CCI”, we reject the hypothesis of “CCI does not Granger Cause EMBI” at 10% significance level. We can conclude that investor sentiment leads the EMBI index.

Table.4: Granger Causality Test results

Null hypotheses	Chi-sq	Conclusion
EMBI does not Granger Cause CCI	1.3174	Do not reject
CCI does not Granger Cause EMBI	4.4590*	Reject

4. Conclusion

This paper tests the relationship between investor sentiment and sovereign risk in Turkey for the period 2004-2010. As a result of cointegration analysis, we do not find long run relationship between investor sentiment and sovereign risk in Turkey. Then, we investigate the short run causality relationship between investor sentiment and sovereign risk in Turkey by applying Granger Causality test. The findings from the Granger Causality test support the one way causality relationship between these two variables. Although we can not reject the hypothesis of

“EMBI does not Granger Cause CCI”, we reject the following hypothesis “CCI does not Granger Cause EMBI” at 10% significance level. Therefore, we find the evidence of the causality relationship from investor sentiment to sovereign risk in Turkey. This finding supports those of Eichengreen and Mody, (1998); Diaz and Gemmill, (2006), Spyrou, (2011) which emphasize the importance of the investor sentiment for country risk. The findings of the paper is important for Turkish government officials and market participants (Spyrou, 2011). Because it is commonly accepted that sovereign risk or spreads are mostly affected by economic

factors. However, the findings of this paper emphasizes that focusing only on economic factors may not provide to reduce borrowing rates and enable the access of Turkey to financial markets. However, sending a strong qualitative signal, that affects investor sentiment in a more direct way and reverses the spiral of pessimism, to financial markets may have desirable effect on Turkish yield spreads (Spyrou, 2011).

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APPENDIX

Table.5: The Results of Vector Autoregression Test

	EMBI	CCI
EMBI(-1)	0.0712 (0.1045) [0.6821]	-0.0827 (0.0912) [-0.9061]
EMBI(-2)	-0.4327 (0.1047) [-4.1330]	-0.0586 (0.0914) [-0.6410]
CCI(-1)	0.2832 (0.1347) [2.1030]	0.4371 (0.1176) [3.7153]
CCI(-2)	-0.0670 (0.1373) [-0.4880]	-0.0860 (0.1199) [-0.7173]
C	0.0108 (0.0033) [3.2057]	-0.0004 (0.0029) [-0.1586]

Note: Standard errors and t-values are in() and [], respectively.

Table.6: Variance Decomposition results
EMBI

Period	S.E.	EMBI	CCI
1	0.029937	100.0000	0.000000
2	0.031109	95.16037	4.839626
3	0.033666	95.56214	4.437864
4	0.034011	94.88502	5.114983
5	0.034445	94.86599	5.134008
6	0.034545	94.78455	5.215455
7	0.034617	94.76154	5.238459
8	0.034645	94.75444	5.245557
9	0.034656	94.74561	5.254387
10	0.034663	94.74597	5.254030

CCI

Period	S.E.	EMBI	CCI
1	0.026149	14.64823	85.35177
2	0.028265	12.98834	87.01166
3	0.028419	13.44616	86.55384
4	0.028427	13.45416	86.54584
5	0.028450	13.58033	86.41967
6	0.028452	13.58890	86.41110
7	0.028456	13.61231	86.38769
8	0.028457	13.61618	86.38382
9	0.028458	13.61990	86.38010
10	0.028458	13.62119	86.37881

Figure.1 : Results of Impulse-Response Test

